

Magnetic Study of Complex Compounds of Thiourea and Ethylene Thiourea with some Uni- and Bivalent Metals

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The molar magnetic susceptibilities of complexes of thiourea and ethylene thiourea with salts of Cu, Ag, Cd, and Pb have been measured on a modified form of the Gouy magnetic balance with a view to ascertaining the nature of chemical bond between the cation and the organic ligand. The results indicate a lowering of diamagnetism on complex formation, suggesting thereby that the chemical bond between the cation and the thio-base is of the covalent type.

Morgan and Burstall¹ measured electrical conductance of some complex compounds of ethylene thiourea with salts of different metals in aqueous solution, suggesting the part played by the co-ordination complexes as compound metal radicals. A magnetic study of thiourea and ethylene thiourea complexes of salts of copper, silver, lead, and cadmium was therefore undertaken with a view to ascertaining the nature of the metal-ligand bond in these complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Metal complexes were prepared by the methods adopted by Morgan and Burstall¹ and by Palmer². The starting materials used for the preparation of these complexes with the exception of ethylene thiourea were either of B. D. H. AnalaR quality or of best technical grade quality. Ethylene thiourea was prepared according to Hofmann's method³. The metal complexes were analysed for their purity by estimating the metal content by the standard methods. In a few cases, the compositions of these complexes were further checked by estimating the carbon, hydrogen, and nitrogen contents.

The method employed for measurement of magnetic susceptibilities was the same as that described by Prasad *et al.*⁴ The reported values are the mean of eight measurements on the same compound.

DISCUSSION

The general lowering of the molar susceptibilities of the complexes along with those of the two organic ligands are presented in Table I in which χ = specific magnetic susceptibility and χ_M = molar magnetic susceptibility.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 143.

2. "Experimental Inorganic Chemistry", Cambridge, 1954, p. 130.

3. *Ber.*, 1872, 5, 240.

4. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1944, 20A, 224.

In the fourth column are shown the molar susceptibility values obtained by adding the molar susceptibilities of the salt and the thio-base. The values shown in the last column have been obtained from the differences between the observed and the computed values of the complex compounds. The molar magnetic susceptibilities of salts, required for computing the values of the complexes on the assumption of additivity of magnetic susceptibilities, have been taken from the literature⁵⁻⁷.

TABLE I

Compound.	$-\chi \times 10^6$.	$-\chi_m \times 10^6$.		% Deviation per ligand molecule.
		Obs.	Computed.	
Cu (2Etu) Cl	0.4742	143.7	145.7	0.70
(Cu, 3Etu) ₂ SO ₄	0.4793	400.5	430.7	2.30
Cu (3Etu) (C ₂ H ₃ COO)	0.4807	206.1	229.6	3.40
Cu (4Etu) NO ₃	0.4949	264.0	276.1	1.10
(Cu ₂ .5tu, (NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O	0.4520	310.1	324.0	1.70
Cd (2Etu) Cl ₂	0.4737	183.3	188.7	1.45
Cd (2 Etu) I ₂	0.3780	227.6	234.8	1.50
Cd (4tu) Cl ₂	0.4844	236.1	236.6	0.30
Cd (4Etu) (NO ₃) ₂	0.4535	202.1	301.4	0.80
(Ag ₂ .3Etu) (NO ₃) ₂	0.4186	270.4	277.1	1.80
Ag (3Etu) Cl	0.5033	226.3	229.5	0.50
Ag (4Etu) NO ₃	0.4880	282.1	288.4	0.56
Pb (2Etu) (NO ₃) ₂	0.3215	172.1	188.2	4.30
Pb(6tu) (NO ₃) ₂	0.4009	320.3	322.9	0.10
Thiourea (tu)	0.5581	42.41	..	..
Ethylene thiourea (Etu)	0.5871	50.88	..	..

In thiourea or ethylene thiourea complexes, the co-ordination is expected to occur through nitrogen or sulphur. For covalent bond formation, there should be maximum overlap of orbitals of the co-ordinating species. This would provide a lower value for the diamagnetic susceptibility of the complex than the sum of the susceptibilities of the constituent molecules, since diamagnetism is a function of $\sum \bar{r}^2$, where $\bar{r}^2$ represents the mean square of the radii of electronic orbits.

From Table I the molar susceptibility of the complex in all cases appears to be less than the sum of the χ_m of the constituents forming the complex. The observed lowering of the magnetic susceptibility on complex formation will represent a change in electron density distribution, which is not confined only to the cation complex but which has also to take into account the cation-anion interaction in the complex compound and the size and electronegativity of the cation. It will therefore not be possible to have a direct correlation between the strength of cation-ligand bond in different complexes and the extent of lowering of magnetic susceptibility. The magnetic data, however, indicate that the association between the thio-base and the cation is of the covalent type.

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5. Prasad *et al.*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1947, 27A, 329; 1950, 31A, 290, 369.

6. Khanna, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1947, 3, 428.

7. Selwood, "Magnetochemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., 1956, p. 78.